

Exploring the Impact of HEC's Proposed BS English General Courses Outlines on Alums' English Skills and Job-Interviews

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Abstract: The study aims to determine whether speaking skills are part of BS English language courses in Pakistan and whether alums encounter speaking English language issues when they pass out from university and enter the market as job seekers. The study hypothesized that prospective employers in the market demand high proficiency in speaking skills. The study carefully examines the outlines of the BS English General Course to determine whether or not oral skills were adequately addressed during the four years of study in Pakistan. Quantitatively, as sample data, 'the old and updated' selected course outlines were analyzed to look into the potential for oral activities in course outlines. For qualitative fifty recently graduated students seeking employment and appearing in various occupations participated in structured interviews. The study recommends that the outlines a significant need for speaking skills-based exercises. Moreover, students are taught through GTM and are demanded to respond as taught through CLT. The findings emphasize the need for course outlines to be updated to meet current standards and emphasize the significance of conversational skill development.

Keywords: Speaking Skills, GTM, CLT, Course Outlines, BS English General Course Alums

1.Introduction

The problem's historical context is that graduates must attend job interviews in order to enter the workforce for the first time (Posthuma et al., 2002). According to Dipboye and Gauglar (1993), organizations that "envisage the imminent job attainment of candidates" use job interviews as their major method of selecting and hiring recent graduates (p. 136). The primary goal of graduates is to secure employment, demonstrating the skills that employers believe are essential to the smooth running of their businesses (Harvey, 2000). Employers would prefer to work with applicants who can contribute significantly and provide rewarding employment. The capacity for effective and fluent English communication is one of the main requirements for employment for graduates (Singh & Singh, 2008).

Speaking is a sign of linguistic competency. Fluency in a language is considered a prerequisite for proficiency

(Gatbonton & Segalowitz, (2005). In Pakistan, children must take English as a second language from elementary school through university. However, speaking English is a challenge for Pakistani and university students. Some need help to speak English after graduating (Esmail et al., 2015).

English has become the lingua franca and language of all media to communicate internationally. Additionally, it is a language of opportunity and success. It is, therefore, a language of the Senate, education, and law in Pakistan (Kirkpatrick, 2012). In Pakistan, English is used in the classroom 90% of the time. For this reason, when attending job interviews, students are expected to speak clearly and concisely. So, for the matter of speaking language, it is always appreciated by prospective employers that job seekers may speak fluently and clearly (Samad, 2014). Shamim (2011) claimed that in the Pakistani context, speaking skills in English have become a must for success in Pakistan's dynamic market, particularly for job seekers leaving academics to enter the economy. Proficiency in English is essential for determining employability, especially during job interviews. Speaking and articulation abilities and speaking skills are often crucial components of a successful job interview to provide graduates with thorough language proficiency (Ting et al., 2017).

High Education Commission (HEC) had course outlines for Bachelor's (BS) for all disciplines (samples are attached appendix-A, B, C, and D). It is crucial to assess whether students face hurdles in speaking the English language after completing their Bachelor's degrees during the job-seeking process and whether speaking skills activities are included in BS English language course outlines. The goal of this project is to close the gap between academic language instruction and the practical language requirements of the job-market. By examining the experiences and opinions of passing students, it seeks to pinpoint areas where the course outlines need to be improved. Considering the increasing significance of English language proficiency in the business, it is also relevant and current. It is anticipated that the findings would provide important insights for educators, policymakers, and organizations shaping the teaching of languages in Pakistan, encouraging a more effective alignment between curricula and the practical language skills required for employment.

The study stated its problems as, even after receiving their BS degrees, students majoring in any field reported needing help communicating effectively in front of prospective employers. This study is fascinating, similar to a study conducted by Chand (2021) in Nepal. Her study deals with students' speaking skills even after getting their degrees. His research focused on the following areas: Speaking difficulties can be caused by a variety of factors, including the instructor and learning style, the course material, overuse of one's native tongue, poor classroom culture and education, and linguistic, social, emotional, and psychological problems. The study recommended altering teaching strategies, rewriting courses, fostering a positive learning atmosphere, maximizing student autonomy, and regularly holding speaking exercises.

Considering the research problem and Chand's (2021) research, this research also looks at students' fluency or speaking issues after completing their degrees during job interviews. However, it found different results as data was collected and the sample varied. The study suggests that existing BS English course outlines should add speaking material (contents) to meet the needs of undergraduate students after completing their degree programs.

Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) primarily aims to understand the pragmatic language requirements of job seekers and their everyday communication. The CLT methodology underscores the intimate relationship between communication and job hunting, stressing the importance of language acquisition for realistic communication (Richards, 2005). CLT emphasizes speaking skills over content and material accuracy, promoting self-expression without overemphasizing grammar using interactive and contextual language for effective learning (Huang, 2011). This study explores the development of practical language skills through real-world assignments, aligning with the research on speaking skills requirements in job interviews. This study examines the success of HEC's language programs in meeting the speaking skill requirements of Pakistani second language learners using CLT as a theoretical framework. This study's philosophical foundation is rooted in pragmatism and constructivism, both oriented towards practical exploration of real-world issues and solutions. A pragmatic approach can directly inform language education practices and enhance employability among job-seeking alums by addressing their speaking skills needs. This study incorporates constructivism to investigate how job-seeking alumni actively participate in language exercises, develop speaking abilities, and use them in practical settings. The

research paradigm, combining Pragmatism and Constructivism, offers a comprehensive exploration of speaking skills needs, considering practical solutions and learners' active participation in the language learning process.

2. Literature Review

In twenty-first-century curriculums, English has become a required language in the majority of countries where it is used as a second or foreign language (Akbari, 2015). Since English is recognized as a global language, learning it improves one's prospects of landing a job, travelling, obtaining a higher education, and leading a better life (Crystal, 1997). Teaching English is viewed as a challenging task, especially in developing countries, since it is mandated in school curricula from the very beginning to the university level and everyone must survive independently. According to Hammer (2001), English is employed in all spheres of human endeavor, including science and technology, education, entertainment, and health. English is used in the majority of modern scientific and technological publications and inventions.

In a similar vein, everyone had to learn English because of the rapidly growing use of technology and information, especially the Internet (Richards & Renandya, 2002). Studying English will help many people advance and have better lives. They believe that speaking the language well will make it easier for them to get employment in the future (Harmer, 2001). Because of the strength of the English language, most people—not only students, but people all around the world—dream of moving to an English-speaking nation where they can live comfortably and receive a superior education. Believed to offer better lives, people are drawn to go to and establish in English-speaking nations (Crystal, 1997). Apart from these benefits, learning English can present a number of difficulties that learners of the language as a second or foreign language must overcome.

2.1 English Language Learning Issues

Training and education in non-English speaking nations. English is now taught in many colleges in nations where it is a second or foreign language, and many schools dedicate their curriculum to teaching challenging jobs. But a lot of students find that learning English is difficult. Courses in schools and universities still include English as a topic. In Phyak (2016) and Akbari (2015). The majority of students in school and university English classes fail because of difficult grammatical patterns and psychological or attitudinal problems with the learners, which leads them to believe that the subject is extremely difficult (Ahmed, 2015). Many elements, including challenging grammatical structures, challenging vocabulary, variation in L1 and L2, motivation, instructional strategies, student attitudes, and many more, and influence language acquisition. There are several reasons why language learners may struggle, including hearing issues, memory loss, speech challenges, mental health issues, introversion, and social, individual, and cultural differences (Oxford et al., 1990). He came to the conclusion that the main causes of students' learning difficulties were their sociocultural backgrounds and learning strategies. In addition to personal qualities, language acquisition may be influenced by learners' social or cultural backgrounds. Students' capacity and willingness to pick up a second language are influenced by various elements such as infrastructure, learning facilities, instructors' attitudes, low student motivation, lack of attention, lack of confidence, and others (Mutiah et al., 2020). Moreover, it is claimed that language learning abilities are intrinsically linked to educational elements like the function of the teacher, the curriculum and teaching resources, the instructor's teaching style, the instructional media, and the infrastructure of the institution (Brinton, 2001). If a teacher adopts a facilitator position in the classroom, students' learning proficiency may rise; yet, if the teacher adopts an authoritarian role, students become passive learners and miss out on opportunities for language practice (Russell, 2017). Thus, learning a language is influenced by more than just an individual's personal learning characteristics; the teacher's presence also causes learning challenges and how the language is taught in the classroom.

As per Akbari (2016), learning strategies are unique instruments that augment the learning potential in a learning strategy that can enhance students' comprehension. She said that people may only be able to acquire a language if they realize how important English is to their daily lives. It indicates that motivation is essential for language acquisition. She added that learning strategies are unique instruments that augment students' learning potential; implementing a specific learning strategy can enhance students' comprehension. She said that people may only be

able to acquire a language if they realize how important English is to their daily lives. It indicates that motivation is essential for language acquisition. Knowing how English is used on a daily basis may encourage learners to pick it up more. Pupils that are motivated show this concentration in their coursework, which expedites learning. Raja and Selvi (2011) discovered that learning challenges were significantly influenced by the environment, attitudes, and teachers' competency. According to them, kids could require assistance comprehending the material if we are unable to establish a supportive learning atmosphere in the classroom and pay attention to their individual learning needs and skills. Learning challenges have also been linked to a teacher's ability; if a teacher cannot explain the material in a way that makes sense to the students or builds on what they already know, the pupils may require assistance in learning the language. Teachers should either motivate students or help them develop a positive mindset about the English language in order to enhance learning. Thus, they discovered that the primary issues with learning English were the classroom atmosphere and the instructional methods of the teachers. Nor et al. (2019) enumerated the following problems with learning English as a second language in their paper. It's widely believed that learning English is difficult. A number of variables affect how well students learn English, such as the role of the English teacher, the availability of a safe space for language practice, the quantity and quality of language exposure, vocabulary competence requirements, poor motivation, and teaching methods.

Guzman et al. (2006) conducted an examination into the "English language difficulties of Korean students in a Philippine Multidisciplinary University" in the Philippines. The purpose of the study was to ascertain the kinds of difficulties Korean undergraduate students in the Philippines encountered when attempting to acquire English as a second language. Mispronounced words, a lack of experience in real-world scenarios, trouble comprehending teachers, a restricted vocabulary, trouble structuring coherent sentences, and trouble expressing oneself are the main obstacles students face in their education. The primary challenge with learning English, according to their research, is accentual diversity in teachers' pronunciation. Their findings indicate that the main reason students have trouble learning English is accentual diversity in teachers' pronunciation. The existence of teachers and the educational environment in the classroom are additional elements that exacerbate this problem. The development of language abilities, including speaking, listening, reading, and writing, can be hampered by learning difficulties.

2.2 Speaking Issues and their Causes

For all language learners who are learning a foreign language, being able to speak English both in formal and ordinary settings is essential. For most people, the most important part of learning a language is being able to converse in English, according to Nunan (1991). Speaking speakers need to be aware of a number of things, such as sociocultural norms like turn-taking, speech rate, length, and pause, as well as language mechanics like pronunciation, grammar, and vocabulary. They also need to be aware of language functions like greeting, asking, and receiving permission (Burnkart, 1998: cited in Heriansyah, 2012). Therefore, it is believed that speaking is the most difficult skill to pick up in a second language. When learning to talk, students encounter several challenges. According to Ur (1991), pupils struggle with inhibition, having nothing to say, having uneven or low engagement, and using their mother tongue. Students are often constrained when trying to speak in a foreign language in the classroom, according to You (1991), since they are worried about making mistakes or getting bad grades. In a similar vein, students are so unmotivated that they remain silent even in situations in which they are not impeded. Insufficient or inconsistent involvement is the third primary problem that students face in the classroom. Talkative or intellectual students may be the class leader, and even if their dominance is managed, there won't be enough time for them to interact. Learners feel safe and at ease speaking in their native tongue throughout class, which helps to avoid misunderstandings and the anxiety of hearing unfavorable comments from their classmates. As a result, many prefer using their native tongue when speaking in class, which makes learning English more challenging. Comparably, Brown (2001) has noted the following problems associated with speaking: interaction, supra-segmental features, velocity of delivery, colloquial language, performance variable, clustering, redundancy, and reduced form. Since connected communication demands speakers to use phrasal form rather than word-by-word, learners may find it challenging to express themselves in the target language. Similar to this, speakers of second or foreign languages are not used to using contracted or reduced versions, even if they are frequently used in fluent

speech. They so have trouble cutting down on some English terms, which makes their speech sound strange. The use of colloquial language by native speakers might decrease exposure and make it more difficult for learners to interact with them. Speaking might be challenging for pupils who are not accustomed with colloquial English. Using corrections, backtracking, and gap fillers excessively can cause a lack of speech velocity; these are also referred to as hesitation indicators. It may be difficult for speakers to communicate rapidly if they do not have the required vocabulary and language patterns, and they can be asked to carry on the conversation. Many non-native English speakers find it difficult to regulate the stress, rhythm, and intonation of their speech since English is a stress-timed language. A variety of problems might affect speaking proficiency, such as the culture of the classroom, poor grammar, and a lack of vocabulary. Age or maturational limitations, aural medium, sociocultural context, and affective aspects are the main causes of speaking difficulty, according to Richards & Renandya (2002). Among many other factors, age is thought to have the biggest impact on language acquisition. It may be simpler for language learners to pick up a second or foreign language if they begin later in life, according to a number of scholars, including Krashen, Long, and Scarcella (Richards & Renandya, 2002). Additionally, many adults who acquire a second language later in life may never be able to speak it as well as native speakers, according to Richards and Renandya (2002). Adult learners may experience difficulty speaking as a result of influence from their native tongue. The second factor affecting speech is the aural channel. The majority of research has shown how crucial listening is to the development of speaking skills (Ur, 1991). Adult learners may experience difficulty speaking as a result of influence from their native tongue. The second factor affecting speech is the aural channel. The majority of research has shown how crucial listening is to the development of speaking skills (Ur, 1991). Learning a language entails becoming acquainted with its social and cultural nuances, therefore in order to converse effectively, learners must be aware of specific customs or speaking cultures of the target language. With addition to the verbal communication systems of language, speakers also need to be conversant with nonverbal communication systems such as body language, facial expressions, eye contact, and many more. Therefore, if sociocultural elements are not grasped, a communication system in the target language may encounter problems. Academics Brown (1994), Khasinah (2014), and Oxford (1990) are just a few who have emphasized the role affective components play in speech issues. Emotions, self-esteem, empathy, anxiety, attitude, motivation, and feelings of discomfort, annoyance, self-doubt, and apprehension are some of the key factors that affect a person's capacity to lower their speech rate when speaking (Oxford, 1990; Brown, 1994).

It is clear from the discussion of the literature review above that second and foreign-language learners may encounter various learning challenges, particularly when it comes to speaking. These could include inhibition, a lack of vocabulary, poor syntax, difficulty pronouncing words correctly, fear of making mistakes, unfamiliarity with the sociocultural communication system, and other issues. In addition to the spoken language system, students must also understand the nonverbal communication system to be proficient in speaking. The two main factors contributing to speaking difficulties are improper vocabulary and mother tongue usage. Many studies on learning challenges have been carried out worldwide, identifying various challenges and their root causes. However, as speaking challenges are the most pressing problem in Pakistani education, this study has concentrated on the challenges Pakistani students face, particularly those at the university level. Few studies have examined how adult learners experience speaking difficulties; most reviewed studies focused on children or were grounded on pedagogical ideas. Adult learners are learning-oriented and self-directed (Knowles et al., 2005). Therefore, they have some experience with problems related to their own. The perceptions of speech inadequacies and attitudes towards speaking obstacles among adult learners are the main subjects of this study. The study also examined whether or not speaking challenges are the same for pupils throughout the world.

According to Rahayu's (2015) research, pupils struggle with speaking English. As a result, the instructor could provide the pupils with practical solutions to their concerns. Additionally, the management has assessed the language Programme to help overcome the challenges caused by human resources' ineffective everyday use of the Programme. It occurs because of their varied educational backgrounds, which makes it difficult for them to speak foreign languages daily and presents a barrier for officials when using everyday language. Management attention is

finally required for this situation to assess potential solutions for the issues with the speaking English everyday language Programme.

According to the results of another study, recent graduates must speak English fluently in order to be considered for interviews (Krishnan et al., 2017). According to Fareen (2018), fostering relationships between academic institutions and business is crucial for students to get employment offers and acquire skills relevant to their field of study. Another researcher, Al Nakhalah (2016), investigated the same topic and found that students' speech difficulties can be attributed to a variety of factors, including shyness, anxiety, fear of making a mistake, and a lack of confidence. He suggests that these problems can be resolved, and that the responsible institution should take this responsibility. According to a study by Afshar and Asakereh (2016), some social issues, issues with instructors, a lack of teaching facilities, and the nation's educational system's curricula were among the major issues that caused problems for first-year students' and seniors' speaking abilities in class and during job interviews. According to Romadlon (2021), alumni's ability to communicate in English is essential to advancing their careers.

Additionally, when alumni take interviews, speaking emerges as the one of the three English language proficiency requirements that is either verified by interviewers or required in the first place. Teaching, learning, and the classroom are all impacted by language. An investigation looks into the possible impact of communication on alumni's edge over competitors. When students enter their real-world situations, classroom exercises and instructional strategies greatly assist them (Ghafour et al., 2023). The above-all debate on the importance of speaking skills needed in interviews laid liabilities of the institute's need to change policies. If the existing policies bring hurdles for alums, they must be settled by revisiting the course outlines. This research finds a gap in that HEC's newly offered HEC course outlines for all BS courses in Pakistan need speaking skills-based content. As a result, alums encounter issues speaking the language. This research gap is settled by recommending suggestions for the curriculum designers and policymakers to resolve these significant issues of upcoming passing out students.

3. Methodology

The integrated emphasis on practical insights is made through understanding the course General English course outline scheme of contents and learner experiences. The study first scrutinized course outlines (old and new ones proposed by HEC, Pakistan for BS students) offered to the students of BS in all subjects in the first two semesters. To calculate percentage variations for fundamental communication skills, like listening, speaking, reading, and writing portions, all contents are separated into four levels, and percentages are calculated. Quantitative data is analyzed by calculating content and through the simple formula of percentages.

Later on, interviews were conducted (focused group). Interviews were based on two parts. The first part of the interviews deals with students' responses regarding the conditions they faced during job-seeking interviews and responses regarding classroom activities when they were BS students. The data is tagged on NVivo for common answers. All the data is judged keeping in view Communicative Language Teaching (CLT). The lens of CLT provided information that either HEC's proposed outlines are in line with students speaking needs or not.

Figure 1
 Communicative Language Teaching Model (Hymes, 1972)

4.1 Quantitative Data Analysis

i. The Old Course Outlines Results

Table 1: Frequencies of Communication Skills in Course Outline of “Introduction to Grammar” ENG-101

Listening%	Speaking %	Reading %	Writing%
10	05	35	45

Table 2: Frequencies of Communication Skills in Course Outline of “Academic and Technical Writing” ENG-201

Listening%	Speaking %	Reading %	Writing%
08	10	25	56

ii. The New Course Outlines Results

Table 3: Frequencies of Communication Skills in Course Outline of "Functional English" GE-105

Listening%	Speaking %	Reading %	Writing%
10	10	35	45

Table 4: Frequencies of Communication Skills in Course Outline of “Introduction to Expository Writing” ENG-205

Listening%	Speaking %	Reading %	Writing%
8	8	47	37

4.2 Qualitative Data Analysis

4.2.1 Interview Part-1

Responses of alums regarding the conditions they have to face during Job-Seeking interviews.

- i. Job interviews are conducted in English.

'All job interviews in which they appear are conducted in English language. Job-seekers are expected to answer fluently, and candidates with little good speaking skills are preferred over less frequent candidates'.

ii. Students are judged for speaking skills in English.

'jury members judge them for speaking skills; the more speaking skills means more intelligent and less speaking skills means less intelligent, that is speaking skills in English is measuring criterion in offering jobs.'

iii. Functional English Language is Preferred over Academic English Language

'Interviewers prefer the candidates with native-like control, that is, social but fluent language is preferred over academic and structured language.

iv. Speaking skills in English are preferred over content.

'Jobs are offered to those candidates who speak fluently; the concept of an intelligent or more knowledgeable person having to face a setback by not getting selected.'

v. Code-switching is discouraged over Speaking skills

'Students are expected to speak in full-fledged fluent English, and they are not allowed to speak switch for language, the margin of second language learners and the phenomenon of world Englishes is not considered.'

4.2.2 Interview Part-II

Responses of students regarding classroom activities when they were BS students.

Q1. Were they taught through interactive methods?

We were taught through the Grammar Translation Method (GTM). We mainly were given quizzes, assignments, and test papers. There were no symposiums, seminars, or class discussions; authority was in the hands of the teacher, and they were just followers. At the end of the semesters, sometimes, we were asked to present for a few marks, and at that time, we were allowed to do code-switching.

Q2. Were they taught through contextual learning?

We were taught through the lecture approach method, black/ white board oriented activities were given to us, and final assessments were also written exams. Contextual studies and oral orientation contents were not part of our course of studies.

Q3. Was there a focus on speaking skills during the study period?

The main focus was on written and reading activities. There was not a single oral exam during our course of studies.

Q4. Were they taught through task-based approaches?

Tasked-based activities for oral speaking skills were separate from our teaching courses. Written and reading tasks were there in our course outlines.

Q5. Were there real-life-based practices in the classrooms?

Teachers use to deliver through code-switching processes; language interference is preferred to communicate well.

5. Conclusion

The quantitative data results show that there needs to be more content based on listening and speaking skills. Old and new course outlines show a need for speaking skills-based content. Old course outlines ENG-101 and ENG-102 contain maximum reading and writing skills of 35%, 25% and, 45%, 56% (Table 1&2) and less reading and writing skills based content of 10%, 05%, and 08%, 10%, 9% (Table 1 &2). New course outlines GE-105 and GE-205 also contain maximum reading and writing skills 35%, 45%, 47%, 37% (Table 3 &4) and less reading and writing skills based content 10%, 10%, and 08%, 08% 9% (Table 3 &4). The quantitative data shows there needs to be more listening and speaking content in the coursed-out lines, either the old or the new.

The results of qualitative data part 1 shows that interviews are conducted only in English; the criterion of judgment during interviews is speaking skills in English; students are expected to speak full-fledged functional or native-like social language instead of academic and code-switching-based language.

The results of the second part of the interviews show that students were taught through something other than interactive or communicative language teaching methods but through GTM. The contextual level is the basic need

to speak fluently, which can be done through CLT, but this is also neglected. Enhance speaking skills through CLT; different teaching techniques are required to apply while hearing again; the situation is sad as speaking skills are not focused. Students gave responses that they needed to be taught through task-based containing speaking skills. The main concern needs to be taught. Only written and speaking tasks were given. Moreover, they were taught mainly code-switching, and they were expected to speak fluent English in interviews.

It is summed up that students are taught through GTM and expected to speak as they were taught through the CLT approach. The study suggests that CLT should be part of our teaching methodology to fill the gap at the student level. It is inappropriate that we teach students through GTM and demand the CLT approach from them. The findings may facilitate collaboration between educational institutions and employers, empowering Students.

The significance of the study in research on "Exploring Speaking Skills Needs of Job-Seekers Alumni: A Study of HEC's Proposed BS English General Courses Outlines for Pakistani Second Language Learners" lies in its potential to contribute valuable insights and bring about positive changes in language education and job preparedness. Here are key points highlighting the significance: it addressing Employability Concerns: informing Curriculum Development: Improving Educational Effectiveness, helpful in enhancing alumni outcomes, guiding policy recommendations, contributing to academic research, fostering collaboration, the ability to fill the gap between vocational employability and academic language instruction, contributing to the improvement of language courses, and ultimately benefiting job-seeking alumni in Pakistan, insights for Curriculum Enhancement, recommendations for Educational Institutions, Enhancement of Employability Skills, Informing Policy Decisions, Advancement of Academic Knowledge, Empowering Alumni: Strengthening Industry-Education Collaboration, Contribution to National Development: From the micro level of a single student's achievement to the macro level of guiding policy decisions and encouraging partnerships that benefit both educational institutions and industries, the study offers significant contributions. For those who want to improve the caliber and efficacy of language learning initiatives within the framework of employability, it is an invaluable tool.

5.1 Key Findings

The study's findings about fluency issues are similar to those of Chand's (2021) study conducted in Nepal. Chand recommended establishing a supportive environment, maximizing learner autonomy, modifying teaching strategies, rewriting courses, and repeating speaking exercises. The main causes of students' incapacity to acquire speaking skills were examined in the current study: a deficiency of task-based approaches, a lack of emphasis on fluency, and a need for more interactive and contextual learning. Students at the BS level are still taught using antiquated and traditional methods.

5.2 Recommendations

Based on the study's findings, here are some recommendations and ideas for the future. The courses need to be updated with new information on fluency. Task-based data and direct teaching methods should be used for classroom communication. Moreover, teaching through audiolingual teaching methods may enhance classroom culture. To increase learnability, teachers must strengthen native-like culture. Speaking skills can be learned by having native or expert speakers tutor in language labs. A curriculum focused on fluency should be created, and practical skills should be integrated. Based on the results, new communicative approaches are recommended to replace the outdated Grammar Translation Method (GTM) approach to ELT. The teacher-centered classroom should give way to a learner-centered one where the focus is on pronunciation and the teacher gives students more opportunity to speak English. The study will help educators, decision-makers, and English language learners (ESLs) focus on suggestions to improve the average conditions of the English-speaking community in Pakistan.

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Appendices

Appendix A

Introduction to Grammar ENG-101

- Basics of Grammar (parts of speech and use of articles)
- Sentence Structure
- Tenses
- Active and Passive Voice
- Punctuation
- Correction of Errors
- Direct/Indirect

Appendix B

Academic and Technical Writing ENG-201

- Introduction to communication

- Types and modes of communication
- Letter Writing
- Application
- Report Writing
- CV Writing

Appendix C

Functional English GE-105

- Developing Analytical Skills
- Transitional devices (words, phrases, and expressions)
- Development of ideas in writing
- Reading Comprehension
- Précis Writing
- Developing argument
- Sentence structure: Accuracy, variation, appropriateness, and conciseness
- Appropriate use of active and passive voice
- Organization and Structure of a Paragraph
- Organization and Structure of the Essay
- Types of Essays

Appendix D

Introduction to Expository Writing GE- 205

- Self-Reflection
- Introduction to the basics of the writing process
- Introduction to the steps of essay writing • Prewriting activities: Brainstorming, listing, clustering, and free writing
- Practicing Outlining of the Essay
- Personalized Learning
- Reflecting on the Learning Process, Learning Styles, Goal Setting, and Learning Plan 3. Oral Presentation
- Structure and Significance, Content Selection and Slide Presentation, Peer Review 4. Critical Reading Skills
- Introducing Authentic Reading (Dawn and non-specialist academic books/texts)
- Reading Strategies and Practice: Skimming, scanning, SQW3R, Annotating, Detailed reading and note-taking, Standard Test Practice: TOEFL and IELTS, Model Review Reports and Annotated Bibliographies 5. Community Engagement
- Student-led brainstorming on local versus global issues, Identifying research problems
- Drafting research questions, Drafting interview/survey questions for community research (in English or L1
- Engaging students in Critical Reading, Presenting interview/ survey information, Fieldwork
- Writing Community Engagement Project
- Identifying research problems
- drafting research questions based on the problems identified
- developing research questions in groups
- Drafting interview or survey questions for community research(in English or L1)

Skills and Job-Interviews

- In-class role-plays of interviews with community members
- understanding interview information, how to present interview or survey information
- Refining the research questions, designing a detailed research plan in groups, dividing the tasks, and deciding the timeline for the completion of the project techniques to develop an in-depth understanding of the issues
- translating the data from the source language to the target language • Sharing the experience of Fieldwork in class orally
- Think-pair-share the findings (group similar issues)
- Individual writing of reflection on the community engagement project and their role in the group
- Brainstorm using creativity for dissemination - cartoons, advertisements for university magazines, or beyond
- Summarize/convert the report to a letter to the editor to highlight the 6. Letter to the Editor
- Types of letters, Format, and purpose of the letter to the editor, Steps in writing letter-to-editor